

SYNTHESIS AND SURFACE MODIFICATION OF POLYETHERIMIDES BY REDUCTION, FOR TAILORED COMPOSITE MATERIALS PREPARATION

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ABSTRACT

Polyetherimide Ultem® 1000 (PEI) was functionalized by controlled reduction of phthalimide groups using sodium borohydride as a mild reducing agent. The new chemical structure of the polymers was fully analyzed by nuclear magnetic resonance, attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infra red, gel permeation chromatography and thermal analysis. According to the degree of chemical modification induced, more colorful polymers with lower thermal stability were obtained. However, the surface modification of polyetherimides by reduction appeared to be a new and interesting way to prepare more hydrophobic PEI for coating and composite materials preparation. Contact angle measurements and infrared confirmed the successful reduction of PEI films or granules.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polyetherimide (PEI) is an aromatic polyimide patented by the General Electric Co. in 1973[1]. This amorphous thermoplastic polymer combines good flame resistance, outstanding electrical properties, high heat resistance, and mechanical strength in a material that is easy to process. All of these excellent properties account for PEI's usage in many electrical applications [2,3]. The fact that it keeps its high strength at elevated temperatures, coupled with good resistance to fuels, lubricants, and coolants accounts for PEI's use in aerospace applications [4-6]. PEI or Ultem® (SABIC) is industrially synthesized via the polycondensation (Scheme 1) of a dianhydride, 4,4'-(4,4'-isopropylidene diphenoxy) bis (phthalic anhydride) (BPADA), with m-phenylene diamine (mPDA).

Scheme 1 : Synthesis of PEI

Chemical modification of polymers is a method used to introduce functional or reactive groups that alter the surface of a material, provide side chain substituents or modify their solubility. It is also a strategy for obtaining new materials that are not readily available, by starting from a preformed polymer. Modified PEI's are already used to prepare functionalized membranes for biomedical

applications [7-15] and membrane contactors for wastewater treatment [16] or gas separation [17]. In-vitro and in-vivo studies have shown that PEI exerts no significant cytotoxicity or hemolysis and allows the attachment and growth of cells [7,12,18]. This biocompatibility associated with the outstanding physical properties of this polymer underline the importance of using functionalized PEI to develop specific membranes [10] or biosensors [11]. Functionalized PEI's have also been used to compatibilize thermoset/thermoplastic blends by the incorporation of pendant functions that can react with thermoset precursors by covalent bonding [19]. The polymer backbone of PEI possesses functional groups (phthalimides) that are accessible for several chemical modifications and different functionalizations have already been described. For example, nucleophilic aromatic substitution, [20] nitro reduction, [18] amination, [17,21] sulfonation, [22-24] and oxidation [25] have been used to modify PEI.

Reduction is also a useful way to modify polymers, [26] especially alkyl-aryl polymeric ketones. Poly(Ether Ether Ketone) : PEEK has been successfully modified to PEEK-OH by carbonyl reduction using sodium borohydride [27].

To our knowledge, there are no examples of PEI reduction using hydrides. The introduction of reactive hydroxide groups into the polymer backbone is very interesting for further chemical modifications, but also affects the wettability or solubility of the material. Later in this paper, we report a first example of chemical modification of PEI by reduction using sodium borohydride.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Polymeric starting material PEI Ultem® 1000 was obtained from Sabic® in the form of transparent, amber colored granules and 50 µm PEI film. Sodium borohydride was purchased from Acros Organics and the dimethylsulfoxide was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol solvent was obtained from Fischer Scientific. All the reagent grade chemicals were used as supplied without further purification.

Polymer Analysis and Measurements.

Proton and carbon spectra were obtained on a Bruker AC 400 spectrometer operating at a proton frequency of 500 MHz and a carbon frequency of 126 MHz. Spectra were acquired at room temperature using deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-d₆) solvent and referenced to an internal tetramethylsilane (TMS) standard. Chemical shifts are expressed here in parts per million (ppm) and the spectral resonances are designated as broadened (b), singlet (s), doublet (d), and multiplet (m). Coupling constants (J) are in Hertz.

Attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) analysis was performed using a Nexus ThermoNicolet spectrometer equipped with a Universal ATR sampling accessory (diamond crystal). The spectra were recorded with 16 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in the spectral range of 650-4000 cm⁻¹. The ATR-FTIR background was recorded in the same conditions.

Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) measurements were calibrated with two standard solutions of polystyrene samples with different number average molecular weights: 1,200; 10,730; 72,450 and 580; 4,910; 38,640. The correlation factor was R= 0.999. The chloroform polymer solutions were analyzed using a Waters 717 plus autosampler, a Waters 996 UV detector, and a 5µm PLgel mixed-C column. The rate of flow was 1mL/min and the injected volume for each sample was 50 µL. The column was kept at 35°C in an oven.

The thermal decomposition of polymers was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a Thermal Analysis® Q50 spectrometer and was measured under nitrogen flow 10 mL/min. Samples of 10 mg were weighed and sealed in aluminum sample pans then heated from 20°C to 1000°C at a rate of 20°C.min⁻¹.

Glass transition (T_g) was recorded on a Mettler Toledo differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) calibrated with indium and operating under nitrogen flow (20 mL/min). Samples of 5 mg were weighed and sealed in aluminum sample pans then heated from 50°C to 250 °C at 10 °C.min⁻¹ twice in order to eliminate all traces of solvent. The transition temperature was measured on the second run.

Contact angle measurements were performed with a Krüss DSA10 and a glass syringe with flat-tipped needle. The measurements of the of distilled water contact angle were performed at room temperature

using the sessile drop technique and an image analysis system including a camera. A 2- μ L pendant drop of distilled water was laid on the surface and a picture of the drop was taken thirty seconds later.

Reduction of PEI film surface with sodium borohydride

Sample preparation PEI films were washed and sonicated for 30 min at room temperature in ethanol in order to avoid contamination of the polymer surface by dust or other residual compounds. Then each film was washed again with cold ethanol then dried in an oven at 80°C for 2 h. Samples were kept sealed in a glass container until surface treatment.

Surface functionalization A film of PEI (1 cm²) was added to a stirred solution of NaBH₄ (60 mg, 1.58 mmol) dissolved in DMSO (3 mL) at 120°C. After 15 min of reaction, the film was washed with an aqueous solution of 0.5N HCl (15 min), distilled water (5 min) and ethanol (15 min), and then dried at 80°C for 2 hours. After drying, the surface of the polymer was whiter and still soft. Samples were kept sealed in glass containers until analysis. After treatment, the transparent surface of the polymer was still smooth but whiter than the pure PEI.

Reduction of PEI granules with sodium borohydride

Synthesis of PEI-OH2 PEI Ultem® 1000 granules (0.50 g, 0.79 mmol) were added at one time to a stirred solution of NaBH₄ (30 mg, 0.79 mmol) in DMSO (10 mL) at 120°C. The yellow polymer was progressively colored orange and dissolved in the solvent of reaction. The solution was stirred for 3 h, cooled to room temperature and precipitated with an aqueous HCl solution (0.5N). The polymer was filtered, fully washed with distilled water and then dried at 80°C for two days in an oven. A light orange powder was obtained. ¹H-NMR starting material (CDCl₃): 7.90 (d, J 8.17, 1H), 7.66-7.33 (m, 16H), 7.05 (dd, J 8.76 Hz, 1H), 1.76. (s, 6H). ¹H-NMR product (DMSO-d₆): 7.85-7.01 (m, 18H), 5.39 (s, 1H), 5.33 (s, 1H), 1.69 (s, 6H). FTIR: OH 3349 cm⁻¹ broad, C-H 1253 cm⁻¹ strong, C-O 1045 cm⁻¹ medium.

Synthesis of PEI-OH4 PEI Ultem® 1000 (0.50 g, 0.79 mmol) was added at one time to a stirred solution of NaBH₄ (60 mg, 1.58 mmol) in DMSO (10 mL) at 120°C. The yellow polymer was progressively colored deep red and dissolved in the solvent of reaction. The solution was stirred for 3 h, cooled to room temperature and precipitated into an aqueous HCl solution (0.5N). The polymer was filtered, fully washed with distilled water and then dried at 80°C for two days in an oven. A red powder was obtained. ¹H-NMR product (DMSO-d₆): 7.85-7.01 (m, 18H), 5.39 (s, 1H), 5.33 (s, 1H), 4.42 (s, 1H), 4.47 (s, 1H), 1.66 (s, 6H). IR: O-H 3349 cm⁻¹ broad, C-H 1252 cm⁻¹ strong, C-O 1044 cm⁻¹ medium.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Surface Modification of PEI Film

Sodium borohydride is known to be a mild reducing agent that can react selectively with aldehydes and ketones to generate the corresponding alcohols. It reacts more slowly with esters, amides, or carboxylic acids so, to reduce these compounds, a more powerful reducing agent, lithium aluminum hydride (LAH), is preferred. However, N-substituted phthalimides undergo reduction by sodium borohydride, which results in the formation of N-substituted 3-hydroxyisoindolinone or a mixture of this compound and N-substituted 2-hydroxymethylbenzamides (2 and 3 in Scheme 2) depending on the amount of reducing agent present [28,29].

Scheme 2: reduction of phthalimide with sodium borohydride

Reduction of N-substituted phthalimide by sodium borohydride is also an interesting step in the synthesis of pharmaceutical compounds [30-32]. Polyetherimides have N-substituted phthalimide groups so the main challenge is to introduce compounds 2 and 3 at the surface of the polymer. Surface modification is an interesting tool for enhancing adhesion or cohesion between different materials in contact. In the general case, an increase of alcohol functions at the surface is a good means to improve surface reactivity or cell spreading, especially for industrial or biomedical applications [15,33-37].

3.1.1 Infrared Spectroscopy

The infrared spectra of the thin sample presented new O-H bond vibrations at 3358cm^{-1} and the decrease of N-C=O vibration at 1733 cm^{-1} confirmed the reduction of PEI film with sodium borohydride (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 : Infrared spectrum of pristine PEI and PEI-OH film.

3.1.2 Contact angle determination

Determination of the contact angle provided valuable information on the wetting properties of the surface and, more precisely, on the upper molecular layer at the surface. The values given in Figure 2 are averages of 9 measurements.

Figure2: Contact angle measurements of water drops on polymer surface.

A PEI film was treated according to the surface reduction protocol but without sodium borohydride in order to estimate the influence of the solvent on the surface modification. This film was called PEI-DMSO. The contact angle of water on the main part of PEI-DMSO film was around $77^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ instead of $83^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ for native PEI and $100^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ for PEI-OH film surface. The large standard deviation on the contact angle of the modified PEI film was related to the surface heterogeneity. Despite the introduction of new alcohol functions, the surface of PEI modified by sodium borohydride was more hydrophobic. The synthesis of new alcohol groups did not improve the wettability of the surface. This unexpected observation might be explained by the participation of these hydroxyl functions in intramolecular hydrogen bonds between the new hydroxyl groups formed and the amide functions left.

3.2 Reduction of polyetherimide granules

The first attempt made to introduce hydroxyl functions on the upper layer of PEI films was promising. However it was quite complicated to increase the chemical reduction of PEI film without its complete dissolution in DMSO. The reduction of PEI granules was used as a model to understand what occurred on the polymer film surface. The polymer was also completely dissolved in order to evaluate the thermal stability of the modified PEI. Granules of PEI were treated with different concentrations of hydride at 120°C for 3h. When one equivalent of NaBH₄ was used, the polymer was completely soluble in DMSO and its color turned to orange. The resulting material was called PEI-OH2. On the other hand, when two equivalents of NaBH₄ were used, the resulting polymer turned into a red powder soluble in DMSO. This new material was called PEI-OH4.

3.2.1 Infrared Spectroscopy

The ATR-FTIR spectra of PEI and its derivatives were obtained to analyze and confirm the chemical structure modifications induced by NaBH₄. The corresponding spectra of PEI Ultem® 1000, PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: FTIR-ATR spectrum of pristine PEI, PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4

On the modified PEI spectra, a broad absorption band around 3350cm⁻¹ associated with the stretching vibration of hydrogen bonded hydroxyl groups and the two considerably lowered absorptions at 1776cm⁻¹ (>C=O symmetric) and 1717cm⁻¹ (>C=O asymmetric) suggest the reduction from amide groups to alcohol functions. As the aromatic rings were not involved in the reaction, their band could be used to determine the conversion ratio of the reaction. The ratio between the height of the amide band at 1717 cm⁻¹ and the aromatic band at 834 cm⁻¹ was reduced from 2.5 to 1.41 for PEI-OH2 and 1.13 for PEI-OH4. These values suggest that 44% and 55% of the amide functions had been reduced for PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 respectively.

It is also important to note that the intensity of the C-N stretching band at 1360 cm⁻¹ was considerably lowered on the spectra of modified polyetherimides, which confirms the opening of phthalimide rings. Additional absorption peaks can be seen in the two spectra, which support the successful reduction of PEI. A strong absorption band at 1252cm⁻¹ corresponding to the stretching of C-H bonds and another at 1044 cm⁻¹ associated with C-O stretching suggests the formation of new alcohol functions. However, the other characteristic absorptions of polymers around 1495 cm⁻¹ and 900 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C-H and aromatic ether group Ar-O-Ar) remain intact and suggest that only the phthalimide functions undergo modifications in presence of sodium borohydride.

3.2.2 Gel Permeation Chromatography

Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) was completed by refractive index and ultraviolet detection to acquire the molecular weight and the polydispersity index of the modified polymers. Each GPC peak observed by refractive index detection correlated with each one observed by ultraviolet detection, and confirmed the presence of aromatic polymers. All the GPC refractive index results are summed up in Table 1. We observed two peaks on the PEI-OH4 chromatogram, with a retention time of 6.30 min for the first and 8.40 min for the last. According to the refractive index results, the first peak had a retention time very similar to that of the unmodified PEI. The number average molecular weight (Mn) increased from 22,444 g/mol to 37,004 g/mol and the weight average molecular weight (Mw) also increased from 55,826 g/mol to 60,892 g/mol. At high concentration of NaBH₄, the amide functions formed might be totally reduced to amines (8 and 9). These amine functions at basic pH due to the NaBH₄ excess might have reacted with the phthalimide carbonyl functions left (4) to form compounds 10 and 11. The apparition of new C=O groups in ¹³C NMR spectra encouraged this hypothesis. Moreover, the second peak at 8.40 min with a Mn of 604 g/mol indicated scissions of the polymer chains, probably the more accessible end chains, due to the excess of hydride. The breakage of the phthalimide groups into two new compounds (aniline and 1,2-phenylenedimethanol) was also observed when N-phenylphthalimide was treated with the same excess of sodium borohydride.²⁶ The chromatogram of PEI-OH2 also presented two peaks: the first with a retention time of 6.4 min for a Mn of 36,627 g/mol and a Mw of 64,830 g/mol; the second with a retention time of 9.3 min for a Mn of 699 g/mol and a Mw of 914 g/mol. However, according to the peak height, the chain scissions were largely less present than in PEI-OH4 sample. These values are very close to those of the PEI-OH4 first peak and suggest that the polymerization of the system occurred before the chain scissions.

3.2.3 DSC and TGA thermal characterizations

The thermal stability of the pristine and modified PEI was measured by thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) and the results are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Thermogravimetric analysis of PEI-OH2 and PEI (A) and PEI-OH4 (B)

The thermogram of pristine PEI presents a one-step degradation pattern whereas the modified polymers exhibit a two-step degradation pattern. The degradation onset temperature is around 521°C for the native PEI compared to a first one around 150°C and another around 353°C for the modified PEI-OH4 sample. The first weight loss of PEI-OH4 corresponds to 0.25% and might be due to the degradation of the low molecular weight polymers observed in GPC analysis. However, the total weight loss of PEI-OH4 is only 3% instead of 53% for the unmodified polymer. The PEI-OH2 sample also shows a two-step degradation pattern with degradation starting at 108°C, which is considerably lower than the PEI-OH4 value. Moreover the second degradation temperature is close to 315°C for a weight loss of around 4.8%. As for PEI-OH4, GPC analysis revealed low molecular weight polymers in the modified sample which might have been responsible for the first degradation step because of their sensitiveness to overheating. However, the total weight loss of PEI-OH2 was higher than that of the pristine PEI, 65% instead of 53%. In both cases, the lower thermal stability observed for the modified polymers might be explained by the partial conversion of the amide groups into their respective alcohol functions. The formation of new chemical groups might have induced an asymmetry in the polymer structure which was unfavorable for the thermal stability. On the other hand, DSC analysis revealed interesting results (Fig. 9).

Figure 9 : DSC thermogram of PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4

After being heated from 50°C to 250°C, the two modified polymers presented a glass transition that was strongly below the reference T_g: 125°C and 169°C for PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 respectively compared to 216°C for the pristine PEI. This diminution of the T_g might have been due to a new conformation of reduced polymer chains. The reduction of >C=O functions into -CHOH would lead to the formation of sp³ carbons (-CHOH) instead of sp² carbons (>C=O). However, the increase of the reduction did not induce a large decrease of T_g. In fact, it was observed that the more reduced the polymers were, the more their T_g were shifted to higher temperatures. This unexpected observation might be related to an increase of the hydrogen bonds in the polymers, which would improve the thermal stability of PEI-OH4.

3.2.4 Contact angle

The reduction of PEI film using sodium borohydride revealed physical and chemical modifications that were responsible for the wetting modification. In order to estimate the real impact of the chemical functionalizations of polyetherimide, contact angle measurements were performed directly on the PEI-OH4 sample. To facilitate these measurements, flat sheets of modified PEI were prepared by pressing the powder between two aluminum plates. The results of the measurements are presented in Figure 10

and are the averages for at least 4 drops of distilled water.

Figure 10 : Contact angle measurements of distilled water on pristine PEI, PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 surface.

PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 prepared by pressing presented highly hydrophobic surfaces with contact angles of $88^{\circ} \pm 3^{\circ}$ and $87^{\circ} \pm 3^{\circ}$ respectively. This suggests that the hydrophobicity of PEI-OH film is intrinsically dependent on chemical functionalizations and not only due to an erosion of the polymer surface. Furthermore, this improvement of the hydrophobicity might be explained by a greater arrangement and interaction between molecular chains. The synthesis of hydroxyl functions might introduce a greater symmetry in the polymer structure. Consequently the number of hydrogen bonds between amide and alcohol functions might have been higher, leading to a marked decrease of wettability. The stiffness induced by intermolecular hydrogen bonded interaction between close amide and hydroxyl groups has already been observed [42].

4 CONCLUSIONS

The surface modification of PEI Ultem® 1000 was successfully achieved by the use of sodium borohydride as a mild reducing agent. The new chemical structure of reduced polyetherimide was determined by NMR spectra and ATR-FTIR. When an excess of hydride was used, the phthalimide groups of PEI were widely broken, giving new alcohol and amide functions on the surface. On the other hand, when one equivalent of hydride was used, an isoindoline function was created at the same time as the opening of the phthalimide ring. Moreover, the changes in polymer color support the presence of these two stages of PEI modifications. This reduction induced a decrease in the number of PEI amide groups which favored the delocalization of the conjugated system. The higher the reduction was, the more colorful the polymers were. The thermal stability and the glass transition temperature remained quite reasonable for industrial processing. An increase in the number of reduced functions induced an increase in the average molecular weight of the modified polymers which may have been favored by the sodium borohydride basicity. Moreover, the slight increase in the T_g observed from DSC analysis correlates well with this increase of chain length. This hydrophobicity was also confirmed by contact angle measurements of $88^{\circ} \pm 3^{\circ}$ and $87^{\circ} \pm 3^{\circ}$ for PEI-OH2 and PEI-OH4 respectively. These phenomena could be explained by the formation of hydrogen bonds between the new hydroxyl functions formed and the amide groups left. The presence of new chemical functions on the polymer surface may be suitable for tailored composite materials preparation.

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